

Supporting Information for

Photoinduced energy and electron transfers at graphene quantum dot /azobenzene interfaces

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Table S1 Detailed description of excited states for isolated AZO.

Excited state	<i>t</i> AZO		<i>c</i> AZO	
	Fold	Open	Fold	Open
1	HOMO-3 -> LUMO	HOMO-3 -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+1
2	HOMO-1 -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO
3	HOMO -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO+1	HOMO -> LUMO+2	HOMO -> LUMO+2
4	HOMO -> LUMO+1	HOMO -> LUMO+1	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-3 -> LUMO+1
5	HOMO -> LUMO+2	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+4	HOMO -> LUMO+1	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+3
6	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+1	HOMO -> LUMO+3	HOMO-1 -> LUMO	HOMO-4 -> LUMO+1
7	HOMO-6 -> LUMO	HOMO-5 -> LUMO	HOMO-3 -> LUMO+1	HOMO -> LUMO+5
8	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+3	HOMO -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+3	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+3
9	HOMO -> LUMO+4	HOMO-4 -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO+5	HOMO-2 -> LUMO
10	HOMO-6 -> LUMO	HOMO-4 -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+6	HOMO-5 -> LUMO
11	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-7 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-2 -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO+1
12	HOMO-6 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-5 -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO
13	HOMO-4 -> LUMO	HOMO-6 -> LUMO	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-6 -> LUMO+1
14	HOMO-3 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+3	HOMO -> LUMO+4	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+4
15	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+2	HOMO-9 -> LUMO+6	HOMO-5 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+5
16	HOMO-9 -> LUMO+6	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+2	HOMO -> LUMO+4	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+2
17	HOMO -> LUMO+4	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+4	HOMO-3 -> LUMO	HOMO-9 -> LUMO+8
18	HOMO-2 -> LUMO+2	HOMO -> LUMO+7	HOMO -> LUMO+4	HOMO-7 -> LUMO+2
19	HOMO-7 -> LUMO	HOMO-2 -> LUMO	HOMO -> LUMO+3	HOMO -> LUMO+7
20	HOMO-4 -> LUMO+1	HOMO-8 -> LUMO+1	HOMO -> LUMO	HOMO-1 -> LUMO+9

Table S2. Reorganization energy, coupling, driving force and Marcus rates for the three processes considered in this study, for the AZO molecule isolated.

	Process	λ [eV]	Coupling [eV]	Involved transitions
<i>t</i> AZO	EET	0.14	0.021	D_{PYR}^* (S ₃ , S ₄), A_{AZO}^* (S ₂)
	PET	0.75	0.009	D_{PYR}^* (S ₃ , S ₄), $D_{PYR} \rightarrow A_{AZO}$ (S ₈)
	PHT	0.64	0.003	A_{AZO}^* (S ₂), $A_{AZO} \rightarrow D_{PYR}$ (S ₈)
<i>c</i> AZO	EET	0.24	0.010	D_{PYR}^* (S ₂), A_{AZO}^* (S ₁)
	PET	1.26	0.010	D_{PYR}^* (S ₂), $D_{PYR} \rightarrow A_{AZO}$ (S ₅)
	PHT	1.24	0.003	A_{AZO}^* (S ₁), $A_{AZO} \rightarrow D_{PYR}$ (S ₅)

Internal reorganization energy calculation for interfaces

When considering the interface consisting of donor and acceptor fragments, one can separately calculate the internal reorganization energy as an average of the backward (λ_{Bw}) and forward transitions (λ_{Fw}) as:

- PET

$$\lambda_{Bw} = E(D^* @ D^+) - E(D^* @ D^*) + E(A @ A^-) - E(A @ A) \quad (S1)$$

$$\lambda_{Fw} = E(D^+ @ D^*) - E(D^+ @ D^+) + E(A^- @ A) - E(A^- @ A^-)$$

- PHT

$$\lambda_{Bw} = E(D @ D^+) - E(D @ D) + E(A^* @ A^-) - E(A^* @ A^*) \quad (S2)$$

$$\lambda_{Fw} = E(D^+ @ D) - E(D^+ @ D^+) + E(A^- @ A^*) - E(A^- @ A^-)$$

- EET

$$\lambda_{Bw} = E(D^* @ D) - E(D^* @ D^*) + E(A @ A^*) - E(A @ A) \quad (S3)$$

$$\lambda_{Fw} = E(D @ D^*) - E(D @ D) + E(A^* @ A) - E(A^* @ A^*)$$

where D indicates the donor fragment and A the acceptor fragment in their excited states (i.e., anionic, cation or excitonic states).

Figure S1 Frontier orbitals of isolated AZO molecules (A – trans, B – cis), C - UV-Vis spectra for isolated AZO molecules.

The opening of the conformation lowers the energies of the frontier orbitals, with HOMO at -6.5 eV and LUMO at -0.6 eV for *t*AZO and -0.4 eV for *c*AZO, which leads to energy gap of 5.9 eV and 6.1 eV, respectively. For *t*AZO HOMO is localized on pyrene, whereas LUMO is located on AZO, which suggests a possible intramolecular charge transfer upon excitation (Figure S1A). Both frontier orbitals for *c*AZO in the open conformation are localized on the pyrene moiety, which suggest limitations in charge transfer ability for this isomer (Figure S1B). For *t*AZO the first excited state is a forbidden $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (HOMO-3 to LUMO), therefore is not visible on the spectra (see Table S1). The first bright peak is at 328 nm, which is related to the second excited state (S_2) and corresponds to a HOMO-1 to LUMO transition ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$). The next peak at 306 nm corresponds to HOMO to LUMO+1 transition. For the *c*AZO isomer, similar absorption peaks are obtained compared to the *t*AZO, albeit blue shifted by 20 nm. In addition, now the first excited state is weakly allowed and it shows as a peak at 454 nm, which corresponds to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (HOMO-1 to LUMO+1) transition. The next peak at 309 nm corresponds to a HOMO to LUMO transition.

From a geometrical point of view, all three processes require less energy for *t*AZO than for *c*AZO. For PET and PHT the amount of energy required for geometrical changes is similar and nearly twice as high for *c*AZO compared to *t*AZO. Considerably lower λ is observed for EET, with the value of only 0.14 eV for *t*AZO and 0.24 eV for *c*AZO, suggesting that (similar to fold conformation) this process might be favored.

The coupling for *t*AZO in open conformation favors the EET process between almost degenerated pyrene excitations at 308 nm and 306 nm and AZO excitation at 328 nm. The EET

coupling for this molecule (21.3 meV) is one magnitude higher than the coupling for both charge transfers. Quite low couplings for all three processes are calculated for *cAZO* in the open conformation and it seems that for this molecule EET (between D_{PYR}^* at 309 nm and A_{AZO}^* at 454 nm) and PET (between D_{PYR}^* at 309 nm and $D_{PYR} \rightarrow A_{AZO}$ at 263 nm) can be competitive processes.

Figure S2 NTOs of AZO's excites states.

Figure S3 Geometrical differences for the optimized tAZO and cAZO structures for the three considered processes. Gray: structure in the ground state geometry; green: structure in the excited state, blue: structure with one additional electron; red: structure with one additional hole. The overlap among PHT, PET and EET is also reported.

Figure S4 Density of states for GQD-*t*AZO as well as partial DOS for GQD and *t*AZO.

Figure S5 Density of states for GQD-*c*AZO as well as partial DOS for GQD and *c*AZO.

Figure S6 The alignment of frontier orbitals' energies for GQD, AZO and GQD-AZO for GQD-*t*AZO (left) and GQD-*c*AZO (right).

Figure S7 Natural transition orbitals for excited states that take part in PHT for GQD-*t*AZO (left) and GQD-*c*AZO (right).

Figure S8 The final geometry of the interface composed of graphene and 42 *c*AZO molecules. Red molecules resemble open conformation of *c*AZO.

Figure S9 The final geometry of the interface composed of graphene and 42 *t*AZO molecules. Red molecules resemble open conformation of *t*AZO.

Figure S10 Total energy equilibration during MD for SLG-*t*AZO (left) and SLG-*c*AZO (right).

Figure S1 The visualization of FMOs for the first MD frame.

Figure S2 Distribution of FMOs' energy for the extracted frames.

Table S3. Coupling analysis for the different interfaces.

Model	Process's type	Involved transitions	Coupling [meV]
<i>t</i> AZO_fold	EET	$D_{PYR}^* (S_4), A_{AZO}^* (S_2)$	46.4
	PET	$D_{PYR}^* (S_4), D_{PYR \rightarrow AZO} (S_3)$	44.9
	PHT	$A_{AZO}^* (S_2), A_{AZO \rightarrow D_{PYR}} (S_3)$	64.3
<i>c</i> AZO_fold	EET	$D_{PYR}^* (S_2, S_3), A_{AZO}^* (S_4)$	9.0
	PET	$D_{PYR}^* (S_2, S_3), D_{PYR \rightarrow AZO} (S_{11})$	8.9
	PHT	$A_{AZO}^* (S_4), A_{AZO \rightarrow D_{PYR}} (S_{11})$	105.5
GQD- <i>t</i> AZO	EET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_7), A_{GQD}^* (S_3, S_4)$	5.3
	PET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_7), D_{AZO \rightarrow A_{GQD}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	0.5
	PHT	$A_{GQD}^* (S_8, S_9), A_{GQD \rightarrow D_{AZO}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	51.2
GQD- <i>c</i> AZO	EET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_3), A_{GQD}^* (S_4, S_5)$	10.3
	PET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_3), D_{AZO \rightarrow A_{GQD}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	4.3
	PHT	$A_{GQD}^* (S_8, S_9), A_{GQD \rightarrow D_{AZO}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	70.4
GQD- <i>t</i> AZO_MD	EET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_7), A_{GQD}^* (S_3, S_4)$	2.1
	PET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_7), D_{AZO \rightarrow A_{GQD}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	0.2
	PHT	$A_{GQD}^* (S_8, S_9), A_{GQD \rightarrow D_{AZO}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	41.5
GQD- <i>c</i> AZO_MD	EET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_3), A_{GQD}^* (S_4, S_5)$	6.9
	PET	$D_{AZO}^* (S_3), D_{AZO \rightarrow A_{GQD}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	0.5
	PHT	$A_{GQD}^* (S_8, S_9), A_{GQD \rightarrow D_{AZO}} (S_{10}, S_{11})$	24.8